

Studies on the growth, spectral, optical and mechanical properties of organic single crystal : 2-[2-(4-Diethylamino-phenyl)-vinyl]-1-ethyl-pyridiniumiodide monohydrate

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Abstract : Single crystal of 2-[2-(4-diethylamino-phenyl)-vinyl]-1-ethyl-pyridiniumiodide monohydrate (EDEASI) has been synthesized by the Knoevenagel condensation reaction method. The synthesized compound was purified by successive recrystallization. Good quality single crystals were obtained by the slow evaporation method. The single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis has been carried out to determine cell parameters. It was found that the title material crystallize in the triclinic crystal system with space group $P\bar{1}$. Crystalline nature of the grown crystal was identified from powder X-ray diffraction pattern. The FT-IR spectrum was recorded to identify the various functional groups present in the compound. The proton NMR spectrum has been recorded to identify the presence of particular hydrogen nuclei present in the synthesised material. The optical transparency range and cut off wavelength of the grown crystal have been identified by UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy studies. Themechanical properties of the grown crystal were measured by Vicker's microhardness method.

Keywords : Organic compounds, single crystal growth, slow evaporation, optical material.

Introduction

In recent years, the pyridinium salts and many of the derivatives have been made on the synthesis and crystal growth of non linear optical materials (NLO) for their vital applications in the field of optical storage devices, fiber optic communication, optical signal processing and optical switching¹⁻⁴. The organic π -conjugated systems possess a high degree of delocalization due to their weak Van der Waal's and hydrogen bonding hence organic crystal exhibit large NLO response, high nonlinear optical susceptibilities and high optical damage threshold than the inorganic materials⁵. The advantages of organic compounds over inorganic materials include flexibility in the methods of chemical synthesis, scope for altering the properties by suitability substituted electron donor and electron acceptor groups in their system^{6,7}. In this present work, we report the method of synthesis and crystal growth and the various characterization of EDEASI.

Experimental

Material synthesis :

The starting materials were purchased from Sigma-

Aldrich, Merck Company and used without further purification. EDEASI was synthesized by the the Knoevenagel condensation of 1-ethyl-2-methylpyridiniumiodide (7.48 g, 30 mmol), methanol (30 ml) and 4-diethylamino-benzaldehyde (5.3 g, 30 mmol) in the presence of piperidine (5 drops)⁸. The above mixture was taken in the 250 ml round bottom flask. Then, the mixture was heated at 60 °C for 6 h. Then the product was filtered using a Whatmann filter paper and purified by successive recrystallization process from methanol at least three times.

Crystal growth :

About 30 ml of the saturated solution of EDEASI was prepared from the purified material using methanol as solvent at room temperature, and it was filtered using fine pore Whatman filter paper. The good quality single crystals were obtained from the slow evaporation method. The grown single crystals are shown in Fig. 1a with dimensions $9 \times 2 \times 2$ mm². The reaction process is illustrated in Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The powder X-ray diffraction analysis has been car-

Scheme 1. The reaction process of EDEASI.

ried out to confirm the crystallinity of the grown crystal using a BRUKER X-ray diffractometer with the CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$); scanning angle ranges from 10 to 60° were used with a scan rate of $0.02^\circ/\text{s}$. Fig. 1b shows the recorded Powder X-ray diffraction pattern of EDEASI crystals. The grown crystals were also subjected to single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis, using a Bruker Kappa APEX II diffractometer with MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) to evaluate the lattice parameter values. It is observed that grown crystal crystallize in the triclinic crystal system having centrosymmetric with $P\bar{1}$ space group. The lattice parameter values were found to be : $a = 8.07 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.20 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 15.02 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = 96.81^\circ$; $\beta = 104.46^\circ$; $\gamma = 104.58^\circ$. The calculated volume is 1025 \AA^3 . The single crystal XRD results obtained in the present work are in good agreement with the literature values⁸.

Fig. 1. (a) Photograph of grown crystal and (b) powder X-ray diffraction pattern of EDEASI crystal.

FT-IR spectral analysis :

The FTIR spectrum of EDEASI was carried out in the range of $400\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in order to identify the presence of functional groups and their vibrational modes in the molecular structure of the compound using an Shimadzu IR Affinity spectrometer by KBr pellet technique at room temperature, which is shown in Fig. 2a. The aromatic C-H stretching is observed at 3105.39 cm^{-1} . The peak at 1631.78 is assigned to the vinyl C-H rocking and C=C stretch. The aromatic ring vibrations were observed at 1591.27 and 1525.69 cm^{-1} respectively. The CH₃ deformation and symmetry bending was assigned to peak at 1462.04 and 1355.96 cm^{-1} . The peak at 520.78 and 999.13 cm^{-1} is attributed to the out of the plane and inplane bending of C-N absorption mode. The band at 773.46 cm^{-1} is assigned to the 1,2-disubstituted aromatic ring.

¹H NMR spectral analysis :

The NMR technique is used to identify the structure of organic compounds. The ¹H NMR spectrum was recorded with DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent at room temperature using BRUKER instrument operating with 400 MHz . The recorded ¹H NMR spectrum of the EDEASI is shown in Fig. 2b. The chemical shift at $\delta 1.141$ is due to the methyl protons in the N-(CH₂CH₃)₂ groups. The peak observed at $\delta 3.407$ ppm is assigned to -CH₂ protons of the N-(CH₂CH₃)₂ groups. The quartet at $\delta 4.729$ ppm and

Fig. 2. (a) FTIR spectrum of EDEASI crystal and (b) proton ¹H NMR spectrum of EDEASI.

triplet at $\delta 1.441$ ppm is due to the CH₃ and CH₂ group protons in the pyridinium N-CH₂CH₃ group. The vinylic protons (HC=CH) produce doublet signals around $\delta 7.234$ ppm and $\delta 7.915$ ppm. The doublet at $\delta 6.755$ ppm and $\delta 7.742$ ppm is due to the four protons in the aldehyde

ring. The *meta*-positions protons in the pyridinium ring produce doublet signals at δ 8.329 ppm and δ 7.724 ppm. The *para* and *ortho* positions of the pyridinium ring protons produce doublet signals at δ 8.451 and δ 8.801 ppm. Thus, the molecular structure of the title compound is confirmed from its ^1H NMR spectrum.

UV-Visible spectral analysis :

The absorption spectrum of EDEASI crystal of 1 mm thickness is recorded using an ELICO SL 218 double beam UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer in the wavelength region 190–1100 nm. The recorded spectrum (Fig. 3a) shows that the grown crystals have no absorption in the entire visible region and near infrared region is an essential condition for the nonlinear optical applications. The spectrum gives two peaks one peak at 276 nm was identified due to π - π^* transitions and another one at 478 nm which is due to the π - π^* transitions. From the absorption peaks, two optical band gaps of EDEASI are determined for these transitions. The band gap corresponds to n - π^* is 3.30 eV and for π - π^* is 5.54 eV.

Fig. 3. (a) Optical absorption spectrum of the EDEASI and (b) variation of H_v with load.

Microhardness studies :

The microhardness was carried out on EDEASI crystal using a MH-112 Vicker's hardness tester fitted with a diamond pyramid indenter attached to the incident light microscope. The selected smooth surface of EDEASI was subjected to static indentation were made for various loads ranging from 10 to 100 g, with a constant indentation time of 10 s in all cases. The Vickers hardness number (H_v) of the crystal was calculated using the relation $H_v = 1.8544 p/d^2$ kg/mm², where p is the applied load in kg

and d is the average diagonal length (mm) of indentation mark. It is observed that the microhardness values increases with an increased up to the load 100 g (Fig. 3b), and above which cracks developed on the surface of the crystal due to the release of internal stresses generated locally by indentation.

Conclusion

The single crystals of EDEASI were grown by slow evaporation method using methanol as solvent. The lattice parameters were determined from single crystal X-ray diffraction and found that it belongs to triclinic crystal system having centrosymmetric with $P\bar{1}$ space group. The grown EDEASI crystals were characterized using powder XRD, FT-IR and proton ^1H NMR analyses. From the UV-Vis-NIR studies, the grown crystal is good optical transmittance in the entire Vis-NIR region. The Vickers microhardness studies reveal that the hardness increases with an increase of load.

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References

1. S. Marder, J. Perry and W. Schaefer, *Science*, 1989, **245**, 626.
2. P. N. Prasad and D. J. Williams, "Introduction to Nonlinear Optical Effects in Molecules and Polymers", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1991.
3. G. J. Ashwell, R. C. Hargreaves, C. E. Baldwin, G. Bahra and C. R. Brown, *Nature*, 1992, **357**, 6377.
4. S. Marder, J. Perry, B. G. Tiemann, R. E. Warsh and W. Schaefer, *Chem. Mater.*, 1990, **2**, 685.
5. K. J. Arun and S. Jayalakshmi, *J. Minerals & Materials Characterization & Engineering*, 2009, **8**, 635.
6. J. Zyss, J. F. Nicoud and M. Coquillay, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **81**, 4160.
7. K. Nagaoka, H. Adachi, S. Brahadeeswaran, T. Higo, M. Takagi, M. Yoshimura, Y. Mori and T. Sasaki, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, 2004, **43**, L261.
8. Suchada Chantrapomma, Nawong Boonnak, Narissara Kaewmanee, Ching Kheng Quahc and Hoong-Kun Fund, *Acta Cryst.*, 2013, **E69**, 458.